

Top View
Scale 1:20

Front View
Scale 1:20

Isometric View
Scale 1:20

Right Side View
Scale 1:20

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:			FINISH:		DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION		
DRAWN			NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE		TITLE:		
CHK'D			Ayan						Robotic Capsicum Harvester		
APP'VD											
MFG									DWG NO.		A4
Q.A							MATERIAL:		Assembly_Final		
							WEIGHT:				SCALE:1:20

Robotic Capsicum Harvester

Assembly_Final

A4

SCALE:1:20

SHEET 1 OF 1